

Research Article

Assessing The Relationship of Ethics and Morals in Information Technology

Aisyah Radhiah Mohamad Azri¹, Nur Adilah Hanim Nordin², Nur Athirah Husna Mohd Faddli³ and Nurulannisa Abdullah^{4,*}

¹ Universiti Teknologi Mara; 2020852818@student.edu.my; 0009-0000-0129-2883

² Universiti Teknologi Mara; 2020489008@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0001-8814-9963

³ Universiti Teknologi Mara; 2020846724@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0004-0388-1066

⁴ Universiti Teknologi Mara; Nurulannisa Abdullah; 0000-0002-5294-9125

* Correspondence: annisa@uitm.edu.my; 019- 3633936.

Abstract: The concept of morality and ethics involves evaluating both good and evil in the context of the rules that govern an institution. But there is some argument about what constitutes morality and the guiding principles known as ethics, particularly in the context of research, which calls into question this idea. While ethics emphasizes a social structure in which those morals are applied, morals determine a person's character. The objective of this paper is to analyze the understanding of ethical and morality arise in the technology development and to identify the ethics and morals that have been utilized in several kinds of fields. This paper collected information and documents from an online database and results from a combination of case studies, observed individual behavior and decision making processes. The findings revealed that ethics and morality in emerging fields were positively related in the edge of technology development.

Keywords: Moral; Ethics; Information Technology; Information Ethics; Information System

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a broader sense, ethics takes into account a person's freedom, responsibility, and sense of justice as well as how they interact with others and the surroundings. It can be said that ethics is generally concerned with human independence when it focuses on the interaction that occurs between humans and the rest of the world. This independence is a must for any impartial assessment of the facts and for ethical decision-making. Independence is shown when a person chooses to put themselves as far away from their influence as possible. As long as this process demands a level of clarity that enables us to assess something objectively and select an acceptable course of action, it will be noticed that selecting an ethical course of action is hard. The distinction between suitable (good) and improper (wrong) intentions, decisions, and acts is known as morality (from the Latin *moralitas*, "manner, character, proper behavior"). Morality can be a set of rules or guidelines that are drawn from a code of conduct that is specific to a philosophy, religion, or society, or it can be a norm that an individual feels ought to be universal. Another way to express morality is as a synonym for "goodness" or "rightness". Although there are some distinctions in their usage, morals and ethics are both used in the plural and are frequently regarded as synonyms. A person's personal standards of what is right and wrong are

commonly referred to as their morals. Even if the word "ethics" may be used to refer to moral principles more widely, it is typically employed to explore questions of proper action in a relatively small number of contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 *Ethics*

Every culture has a set of laws that establish the boundaries of what is considered appropriate behavior. The individual rules all come together to produce the moral code by which a community lives, and they are frequently articulated in statements about how individuals should behave. Unfortunately, because there are so many different regulations, it can be confusing for people to know which one to follow.

The Ancient Greek word *thikós*, which means "relating to one's character," is the source of the English word *ethics*, which itself is derived from the root word *êthos*, which means "character, moral nature." This word was translated into Latin as *ethica*, from which it was taken into French as *éthique*, and finally into English. A subfield of philosophy known as ethics is focused on how people behave, particularly how they act in social situations. In order to understand what is morally right or wrong, just or unjust, ethics investigates the intellectual justifications for our moral judgements. In a broader sense, ethics considers how people interact with one another and with nature, as well as their own freedom, responsibility, and sense of justice (Singer, 2018).

According to Baker's (2008), the fundamental concepts of ethics are "should and ought" in life. However, ethics also relates to the values of acceptable and unacceptable behavior. The term "ethics" is not just a phrase; it refers to understanding and adopting moral values in our daily life (Baker, 2008). There are many different types of ethics and virtues that differ from one situation to another (Baker, 2008). Aristotle pointed to two within our soul. The first engages in reasoning and the second in that "cannot itself reason" (Kraut, 2010). However, in order to become "virtuous and practically wise" we must go through the two stages: develop proper habits in childhood and gain "practical wisdom" (Kraut, 2010). And only when the two fuse, are the ethical virtues fully developed (Kraut, 2010)

Information technology (IT) ethics have been gaining a lot of attention recently. Most people rely on technology in both their personal and professional life, and it is practically ubiquitous (Nissenbaum, 1998). Data storage, utilization, and transmission between various computer systems are all made available by information technology. In a wide range of sectors, including healthcare, banking, education, and more, people rely on IT. It is important to understand why ethics are important in information technology. The right use of information technology is therefore necessary to appreciate its full significance and enhance human development. Ethics must be taken into consideration in the application and development of information technology. This will ensure that societal problems are not amplified and spread by technology.

2.2 *Moral*

A moral, commonly referred to as a message or the lesson to be gained from a story or an event, originates from the Latin term *morālis*. The moral may be implicitly conveyed in a maxim or left up to the listener, reader, or viewer to decide for themselves. A moral is also a lesson learned through a tale or from experience. In another sense, morals are the accepted norms of conduct that allow individuals

to coexist peacefully in groups. While morality refers to what is sanctioned by societies as proper and appropriate. Most people have a tendency to behave decently and obediently.

Morality often calls for putting society ahead of one's own short-term interests. Amoral individuals or entities do not care about right or wrong, whereas immoral individuals or entities commit wicked deeds. The term "morality" refers to the particular values held by a given community at a certain moment. Morality has historically had a strong connection to religious traditions, but today the secular world recognises its importance as well. Businesses and governmental organizations, for instance, have codes of ethics that personnel are obliged to follow and abide by.

Several main technological advancements that raise issues of morality and ethics such as nuclear technology, biotechnology, and information technology (IT). The main moral or ethical problems with technology include gender, health problems, employment displacement, and ethical dilemmas. In terms of IT, the topic of whether it is morally right or wrong to share confidential information within a company is brought up. Utilizing computer programmes, businesses can gather data on individuals and even utilize that data for their own gain without regard to morals.

2.3 Information System

Technological advances make it easy for users easily modify records, making concerns about the accuracy and reliability of the data. Utilisation of technologies have the ability to bring about a great deal of harm among the defenceless, which is unethical. Such a problems, which resulted in a number of health issues, is shown by the fact that nuclear technology has the potential to kill countless people and further ruin the environment. In addition, numerous persons who were impacted by nuclear pollution, such as those seen in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, are thought to have genetic conditions. These effects could negatively impact the afflicted persons' future generations.

The components of modern technology that raise moral and ethical questions need to be recognised and handled with regard for all parties involved. Some philosophers argue between ethics and morality. However, a lot of individuals misinterpret the terms morality and ethics when referring to subjective verdicts, deeds, or ideals. Morals are the standards for appropriate behavior in a society with democracy. Although morality can change over time, it nevertheless serves as a benchmark by which we determine what is good and wrong.

3. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this paper is to assess the relationship between ethical and morality arise in the information technology and to identify the utilization of ethics and morals in various fields. An analysis has been conducted by reviewing previous literatures including researches, papers and other sources to identify the needs. A literature review surveys books, scholarly articles, and any other sources relevant to a particular issue, area of research, or theory, and by so doing, provides a description, summary, and critical evaluation of these works in relation to the research problem being investigated. This study will first review various meanings of ethics and morals and their characteristics. Based on this understanding, a classification method will be developed to categorize and identify the relationship between ethics and moral in the selected field.

4. FINDING

4.1 *Business*

Corporate business environments demand high standards of morality and ethics. Ethics and morality are frequently used together, although they are completely different conceptions that require careful differentiation to prevent misunderstanding. Depending on the environment they live in, various people have different ethics and morals. In a business set up, issues related to ethics are based on an individual's good conduct or misconduct in relation to the workplace expectations (McHenry, 2003, p. 1). All employers require their employees to be morally upright.

Each party to a contract has a responsibility to carry out their responsibilities effectively and on time. Whether it's cash, goods, or services, each party must exchange something of value. Morals and ethics both have a place in business, even though these concepts are not typically associated with value. Consider a newly established company that has only recently opened for business. Their recent public relations have been mediocre, despite their above average sales. Due to their moral failings and unethical actions, they might be able to land a few contracts with smaller businesses, but they have very little chance of growing as a business. While morality and ethics clearly play a vital role in business, the obligations outlined in each building contract are generally based on legal requirements rather than just morality and ethical behavior.

When a party signs a contract, it could have responsibilities that go against their morals but not necessarily against the law. Unfortunately, if any of the contractual responsibilities go against company ethics, a corporation almost always cannot break the agreement. The contract may only be invalid when laws are broken. The main difference between ethical obligations and contractual obligations is that, if a party does not uphold them, there are no legal consequences. In contrast, if one party breaches a contract, the offending party may face legal repercussions. Laws, which are the rules and regulations that law enforcement enforces, are contractual obligations. Ethics, on the other hand, are the accepted social standards of a particular group or culture.

4.2 *Social Aspects*

In the words of Victor and Cullen (1988, p. 101), there is an increasing belief that organizations are social actors accountable for the ethical and illicit conduct of their workers. This opinion is supported by the widespread agreement that situational influence can improve both morals and immoral behavior. When moral surroundings are taken seriously, a fundamentally social picture of the good life emerges, with participants cooperating and competing but at least having shared ideals. As a theoretical and useful concept of moral ecology, it connects environmental philosophy, notably lessons from the "tragedy of the commons" to the moral and social worlds. It implies that the idea of moral ecology offers a convincing representation of real-life human behaviors.

A word of caution beforehand. It seems likely that the perceived moral ecology has an equal impact on behavior as the real moral ecology. According to an examination done at the individual level, a person's perception of the moral context affects their choices and actions more than the actual moral environment would (Victor and Cullen, 1988). Of course, because other players in the ecosystem act on people's perceptions, moral ecology can have an impact regardless of how they perceive the world. Individuals can act against their views of a moral ecosystem that does not support them, much as in the case of whistleblowers. However, even the "objective" moral ecosystem is largely influenced by the attitudes, commitments, and intents of its participants. One of the challenges facing participants in moral ecology is its complicated subjective nature. Measuring moral ecology likewise faces substantial challenges due to this complexity.

The moral ecosystem, like the other parts of the paradigm, influences behavior rather than causing it in most cases. It also alters in shape and strength depending on the times and circumstances, just like the other parts of the model. As a result, while some circumstances may yield a high degree of agreement about wrongdoing, other circumstances can give room for individuals with different personalities, moral convictions, or skill sets to make their case. Due to the fact that it both impacts and is impacted by the individual, this aspect is more complex than the others.

4.2.1 Ethics Codes and Moral Ecology

Ethics codes are becoming more prominent and prevalent as a result of the belief that they help to define responsibilities and prevent unethical behavior (Harrington, 1996). There is hardly any work that really evaluates how professional codes affect professionals' behavior. Professionals in the field of computing occasionally utilize professional codes as justifications for or against specific design decisions. Even though some of our 24 moral role models had served on committees to draft codes, it is interesting to note that none of them mentioned the importance of professional ethics codes in their interviews with moral role models in computers (Huff and Rogerson, 2005; Huff and Barnard, n.d.). There was a lot of chance to talk about the impact of codes because everyone was particularly asked to name influences on their behaviour during these open interviews, which lasted longer than three hours apiece. We may discover this conflicting pattern of rule effects in the research on organizational ethical codes. The basic objective of organizational ethics codes is to officially state the organization's point of view on moral issues. Some of them have definite rewards, sanctions, or punishments, and they outline broad principles and procedures.

There are many varieties in this area. For instance, Marnburg (2000) identifies 16 fundamental principles that organizational ethics codes frequently contain and groups them into four major categories: capability (creating as much value as possible), integrity and equality, stability (keeping commitments and expectations), and/or protecting the future (taking care of the environment and future generations). On each of these dimensions, codes differ greatly from one another, and presumably moral ecology is no different. Compared to smaller organizations, larger corporations or organizations are more likely to have ethics codes. Only 25–33% of organizational ethics codes have formal processes in place to deal with violations. It is hardly surprising that these codes may have distinct behavioral impacts than those that have no formal repercussions. These compliance-based rules (Paine, 1994; Weaver and Trevino, 1999) usually focus on controlling the behavior of their staff in order to reduce the prevalence of illicit conduct. They maintain this control by strictly adhering to rules and regulations. However, everything that is not expressly forbidden is frequently taken to mean that it is allowed.

4.2.2.1 Organizational Moral Ecology

The practical limitations, moral attitudes and working conditions for a company's employees are undoubtedly impacted by the moral ecology that it cultivates and upholds. The unspoken expectations and guidelines that a corporation has for its employees have a greater impact on the moral ecosystem than any written code or set of principles. A business with a caring ethical culture prioritizes providing excellent customer service. The obligation to "workers, management, and the community" is of secondary importance. Financial returns are least important in this situation. Climate regulations is the propensity of an organization to make ethical decisions based on guidelines created by outside parties, such as laws or professional codes. Using internally created codes to make decisions is referred to as the rule's climate. Due to the instrumental environment, the main drivers are self-interest and

financial gain. Last but not least, the independent atmosphere characterizes occupations where individuals are reminded to preserve their own moral principles. The greatest mean score determines the impression of the dominant environmental type, or moral ecology, in these surveys, which derives a mean score for each of these five climate types.

4.3 Healthcare

A good use of technology is one which improves human physical, mental, spiritual, and moral well-being. It can help people become healthier, more educated, more loving and better at making moral decisions. Bad or overuse technology will do the opposite such as make us sicker, less educated, less loving of others, and worse at making moral decisions. Technology often simply makes actions easier for us and we want good technology that will facilitate good actions, not bad technologies that will facilitate bad actions.

Ethical values are essential for any healthcare provider. Ethics within healthcare are important because workers must recognize healthcare dilemmas, make good judgments and decisions based on their values while keeping within the laws that govern them. To practice competently with integrity, nurses, like all healthcare professionals, must have regulation and guidance within the profession. It is important for the nurse to understand all privacy guidelines with regards to patient care and patient identifiers (Epstein B, 2015).

Other than that, ethical values are also essential for all healthcare workers. Ethical practice is a foundation for nurses, especially those who deal with ethical issues daily. Ethical dilemmas arise as nurses care for patients. There are four main principles of ethics such as autonomy, beneficence, justice, and non-maleficence (Haddad, L. M, 2022). Each patient has the right to make their own decisions based on their own beliefs and values (Morrell TJ, 2019). This is known as autonomy. A patient's need for autonomy may conflict with care guidelines or suggestions that nurses or other healthcare workers believe is best. Healthcare workers also have a duty to refrain from maltreatment, minimize harm, and promote good towards patients (Haddad, L. M, 2022).

In addition this duty of particular treatment describes beneficence. Healthcare workers demonstrate this by providing a balance of benefits against risks to the patient. Assisting patients with tasks that they are unable to perform on their own, keeping side rails up for fall precautions, or providing medications in a quick and timely manner are all examples of beneficence (Haddad, L. M, 2022). Many organizations have ethics boards in place to review ethical concerns. It is also important to advocate for patient care, patient rights, and ethical consideration of practice (Haddad, L. M, 2022). Ethics inclusion should begin in medical school and continue as long as the healthcare professional is practicing.

5. DISCUSSION

Information technology (IT) ethics have attracted a lot of attention recently. Most people rely on technology in both their personal and professional lives, and it is practically ubiquitous. In critical industries like healthcare, banking, education, and more, almost everyone depends on IT. Understanding the value of ethics in information technology is crucial. Other than that, ethics are a standard that helps to ensure people behave honestly. IT is still being developed, monitored, and used in a way that is based on ethics. Personal information must not be tainted or used in any way that is

harmful or negative. Technology ethics must advance along with technology's power in order to protect the people and organizations that rely on it.

After that, keeping the human element of technology in place is a part of information technology ethics. Human values and attitudes are employed to ensure that the systems on which we rely can be maintained and continue to provide useful, beneficial gains to meet our needs. Information technology has significantly improved human health. Equipment for hospitals and medical supply companies frequently uses information technology in their manufacturing processes. An unborn child can now be seen long before it is born thanks to information technology. These information technology developments should be utilized to improve human health. However scenarios arise where it is used unethically in health matters. For instance, information technology can be utilised to encourage abortions or to identify an unborn child's gender with the goal of aborting the child if it is not what the parents were hoping for.

Moral conflicts arise when good and evil are in conflict with one another. The question of whether it is ethically proper or bad to exchange secret information within an organization comes up often in the context of IT. Businesses can collect data on people using computer programmes and even use that data for their own advantage without regard to morality. Users' ability to swiftly update records made available by information technology raises questions about the quality and reliability of the data. In addition, could genetic engineering improve or impair life quality? These are a few of the outstanding ethical issues. Additionally, biotechnology raises certain ethical questions. It is difficult to defend the use of living human beings for research and other technological breakthroughs. For instance, women who are unable to conceive might undergo the vitro fertilization procedure. Because these practices go against their philosophies, religious organizations are against them.

When it comes to ethical or moral issues in information technology, gender is an important consideration. Most frequently, prejudice against women is manifested in a variety of technical developments. For instance, it is believed that men are more productive than women in systems of manufacturing. Males have developed and continue to make many technical advances, and they subsequently construct the systems to favour their gender, which has an influence on the question of gender equality. For instance, the computer business is more male-dominated since women like straightforward subjects. Many female students avoid majors in science, technology, engineering, and math, or if they do, they frequently drop out due to the intimidating environment.

6. CONCLUSION

The study has investigated and identified the relationship between ethical and morality arise in the information technology development and the utilization of ethics and morals in various fields. The investigation led to identifying various meanings of ethics and morals and their characteristics since it has different implications for different fields.

The study has contributed to the understanding of why ethics are important in IT. The findings proved that ethics serve as a guide to help people act honorably. Apart from that, keeping the human element of technology in place is a part of information technology ethics to ensure that the system we rely on provides benefits to meet our needs. In morality, it is an issue in the IT field such as sharing confidential information always becomes the point of discussion whether it is right or wrong. This is because IT allows users to modify and alter the records which will interfere with the authenticity of the records.

The study also assesses the ethical and moral issue of IT in various fields. It comes to the conclusion that almost everyone depends on IT in key sectors like business, healthcare, banking, and education. The analysis revealed that ethics and morality in those emerging fields were positively related in the edge of technology development.

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